

ANTIPARASITIC POTENTIAL OF *Allium fistulosum* (GREEN ONION) CRUDE EXTRACT ON HELMINTHS OVA

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Abstract. *Allium fistulosum*, also known as green onion, is a perennial plant that is a well-distinguished member of the *Amaryllidaceae* family, and has been considered to be a potential antiparasitic agent against *Ascaris lumbricoides* and *Trichuris trichiura*. This experimental research aimed to determine the anti-parasitic potential of *A. fistulosum* crude extract against ova of helminths, specifically, *A. lumbricoides* and *T. trichiura*. Stool specimens were collected from children to evaluate the extent of structural damage parasite ova. Two diagnostic techniques were employed, namely direct fecal smear and the formalin-ether sedimentation method to isolate the ova. The treated samples were incubated for varying periods to determine the most effective and rapid action of the crude extract on the ova. The study achieved a percentage yield of 14.29%, demonstrating that the extraction method was effective in obtaining a substantial amount of crude extract. In addition, the fresh extract, 75%, and 100% crude extracts were identified as the most effective concentration. A 7-day exposure to *A. fistulosum* extract resulted in significantly greater effectiveness compared to shorter durations of 24, 48, and 72 hours. The study also reveals significant total changes in both qualitative and quantitative parameters, highlighting the impact of the *A. fistulosum* crude and fresh extracts. Moreover, the study reinforces the value of integrating scientifically supported herbal treatments into modern healthcare systems as a viable and accessible approach to managing parasitic infections.

Keywords: ascariasis, direct fecal smear, period of incubation, sedimentation technique, trichuriasis

I. INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Organization (WHO), about 80% of the world's population depends on medicinal plants for their primary healthcare needs due to their accessibility, effectiveness, and minimal side effects (Bhatia et al., 2021). These plant extracts contain active components, such as phenolics, flavonoids, stilbenes, and tannins, that exhibit broad biological activities including antimicrobial properties. Parham et al. (2020) emphasize that these compounds can serve as potential sources for developing antimicrobial drugs and food preservatives.

Despite advances in modern medicine, gastrointestinal (GI) parasitic infections remain a significant public health problem worldwide, especially in low- and middle-income countries. Kuete et al. (2015) report that intestinal parasitic infections, particularly those caused by helminths and protozoa, disproportionately affect impoverished communities. Globally, approximately 4.5 billion people are at risk of parasitic infections, with over two billion cases associated with morbidity and mortality each year (Eyayu et al., 2021). The WHO estimates approximately 800–1000 million cases of *Ascaris lumbricoides* infections, 700–900 million cases of Hookworm, 500 million cases of *Trichuris trichiura*, and millions more of protozoan infections such as *Giardia lamblia* and *Entamoeba histolytica/dispar*. These infections contribute significantly to the global disease burden, especially among vulnerable populations like children aged 2 to 4 years (Unasho, 2013; Tigabu et al., 2010).

The incidence of parasitic infections is linked to poor sanitation, unsafe drinking water, contaminated food, malnutrition, and overcrowding (Dangela, 2023). Additionally, the increasing emergence of multidrug resistance among parasites and adverse effects associated with synthetic anthelmintic drugs highlight the urgent need for alternative therapeutic interventions. Băieș et al. (2023) stress the importance of shifting focus toward medicinal plants as promising sources of new antiparasitic agents.

Among plants studied for antiparasitic properties, the *Allium fistulosum*, a perennial plant in the *Alliaceae* family of onions, often known as "murang sibuyas". It is known for its sulfur-containing compounds and rich phytochemical profile, and has shown antimicrobial and antiparasitic potential (Balkrishna et al., 2023). Furthermore, it can flourish in regions not subject to heat or excessive rainfall, but it necessitates a mild climate; however, green onions have *fistulosum* leaves and do not develop a true bulb (Alejandrino et al., 2021). *A. fistulosum*, also referred to as green onions, scallions, Japanese bunching onions, Welsh onions, onions, or spring onions, is a well-distinguished member of the *Amaryllidaceae* family (Xing et al., 2023). Sahiba et al. (2022) stated that *A. fistulosum* is a vegetable predominantly cultivated and collected for its piquant taste. The extensive presence and appeal of *A. fistulosum* in spicy vegetable markets worldwide serve as evidence of their substantial influence on global food security, culinary diversity, and nutraceutical benefits (Zhao et al., 2021). Furthermore, green pseudo-stems, leaves, and undeveloped bulbs of this plant are highly valued for their use in salads, stir-fries, garnishes, and other culinary preparations (Singh et al., 2020). The majority of these vitamins have significant biological activities, such as antioxidants and anti-microbial, anti-obesity, and anti-cancer agents (Sung et al., 2018). Moreover, spring onion is abundant in volatile sulfur-containing compounds and can prevent or treat certain parasitic protozoal and helminthic diseases (Cheraghipour et al., 2020).

Extensive research has highlighted the antiparasitic properties of *A. fistulosum* against various parasites, yet its efficacy against the resilient ova of soil-transmitted helminths, such as *A. lumbricoides* and *T. trichiura*, remains underexplored. These helminth eggs are a major source of environmental contamination and reinfection, particularly in tropical and subtropical regions. Most existing studies focus on adult or larval stages, leaving a critical gap in understanding the potential of *A. fistulosum* to inactivate parasite eggs. This study aims to evaluate the antiparasitic potential of fresh and crude *A. fistulosum* extracts specifically against helminth ova, addressing a significant need in global health. In the context of medical technology, where accurate diagnosis and treatment of parasitic infections are vital, discovering effective natural agents like *A. fistulosum* could improve disease management, particularly in developing countries where children are most at risk. Furthermore, this research supports efforts to combat drug resistance and contributes to enhanced diagnostics, better therapeutic strategies, and stronger public health programs targeting parasitic diseases.

Therefore, this study has significant potential in addressing the global health challenges posed by parasitic diseases. It can contribute valuable insights in the field of pharmaceuticals and medicine toward the development of effective anti-parasitic medications and create opportunities for new therapies that manage high-prevalence parasitic infections. Furthermore, it may help overcome critical issues such as drug resistance, which remains a major threat to public health. Beyond healthcare, the study's applications extend to agriculture, where it can serve as a natural pesticide or water treatment to control parasitic contamination in crops and livestock, enhancing food safety and reducing economic and life losses from parasite-related diseases.

Statement of the Objectives

The study aimed to determine the antiparasitic potential of *A. fistulosum* leaves extract against helminths. Specifically, the objectives were achieved in a duration of one month, from March to April 2025:

1. To determine the percent yield of *A. fistulosum* crude extract
2. To assess the concentration of *A. fistulosum* crude extract that exhibits antiparasitic potential on helminths in terms of:
 - a. Period of Incubation
 - b. Total Changes
 - b.1 Quantity
 - b.2 Characterization of the changes in the appearance of ova

II. METHODOLOGY

Research design

The researchers utilized an experimental research method. The crude extract from *A. fistulosum* was made in different concentrations, and the fresh extract was also prepared. The different concentrations and the fresh extract are added directly to the test tube glass containing the stool suspension, and through microscopy, the reaction was examined and was described based on different parameters.

Study Site and Sample Collection

This study was performed at the research laboratory of the Center for Natural Sciences of Saint Mary's University, Bayombong. Plant sample were purchased at NVAT, Bambang. The biological samples were collected from children's stool samples in Don Mariano Marcos and Barangay Salvacion, both in Bayombong.

Specimen Identification

The plant sample was submitted at College of Forestry, Environment and Resources Management at Nueva Vizcaya State University, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya for its taxonomic identity and it was identified as green onion with a scientific name of *A. fistulosum*.

Data Gathering Procedure

Collection and Maceration of A. fistulosum

A 20kg two (2) sacks of *A. fistulosum* leaves were washed and cleaned with distilled water, then sliced into pieces. The plant samples were air-dried for seven days until thoroughly dried and then ground to a fine powder with a blender machine. The extraction was performed by soaking 350 g of the pulverized *A. fistulosum* leaves and 95% ethanol to extract bioactive compounds (Oyawoye *et al.*, 2022). To avoid evaporation, the mixture was kept at room temperature for 48 hours in a sterile flask covered with aluminum foil. A filter paper and a funnel were used to separate and obtain the residue and filtrate. The filtrate was obtained as an extract and kept in the refrigerator. The crude extract was then subjected to drying by removal of the solvent by a Rotary Evaporator (Rota-vapor R300) below 40°C to evaporate the solvent and get the crude extract (Fonkeng *et al.*, 2015; Assefa *et al.*, 2016). The fresh extract was prepared by squeezing the fresh plant sample directly into the beaker and stored in the refrigerator.

Percent Yield

The yield of the crude extract was calculated in grams and converted into percentage. The yield is the amount of crude extract obtained from the plant powder. In practice, it is determined by the ratio of the weight of the solids content after evaporation by the weight of the dry powder of the plant material used for the extraction, multiplied by 100 (Dagne *et al.*, 2021). The percentage yield was calculated by:

$$\text{Percent yield} = \frac{\text{Weight of dried crude extract}}{\text{Weight of dried plant sample}} \times 100$$

Preparation of the Different Concentrations of Ethanolic Crude Extract

The ethanolic extract was mixed with distilled water to form a liquid solution. Adapted from the study of Moya *et al.* (2019), an analytical balance was used to measure the following concentrations in four (4) different beakers:

Collection and Preparation of Helminths for the Antiparasitic Activity

Stool samples were collected from children after obtaining parental consent and providing proper collection instructions. Samples were placed in sterile containers while wearing gloves to prevent contamination. Clean, uncontaminated morning samples were preferred; if immediate processing was not possible, samples were preserved with formalin or polyvinyl alcohol or kept refrigerated.

The presence of *Ascaris lumbricoides* and *Trichuris trichiura* ova was examined using the direct fecal smear (wet mount) method. About 1–2 mg of stool was mixed with normal saline (0.9%) and Lugol's iodine on a microscope slide. The slide was observed under 10× and 40× magnification to identify and characterize the parasite ova.

Sedimentation Technique

Sedimentation techniques use fluids with lower specific gravity than the parasite organisms, thus concentrating them in the sediment, which allows for easier isolation of helminth ova (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2019). Moreover, it is used for general diagnostic laboratories because they are simpler to implement and less prone to technical faults. The researchers utilized the formalin-ethyl acetate sedimentation technique, a diphasic sedimentation technique that eliminates the issues associated with ether flammability and can be utilized with specimens preserved in 10% formalin, merthiolate-iodine-formalin, or sodium acetate-acetic acid-formalin. Furthermore, the formalin-ether concentration technique, also known as the formalin-ethyl acetate sedimentation method, is a frequently used sedimentation technique for the identification of intestinal protozoa in preserved stool samples (Becker *et al.*, 2011).

The procedure for the formalin-ethyl acetate sedimentation technique was adopted from the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. Two to three grams of stool was mixed with 7 mL of 10% formalin, strained into a conical tube, treated with 3 mL of ethyl acetate, and centrifuged at 1500 rpm for 5 minutes. After removing the supernatant, 3 mL of formalin was added to resuspend the sediment.

Seven Wasserman test tubes were prepared and labeled for different concentrations (25%, 50%, 75%, 100%), negative and positive controls, and fresh extract. Equal volumes (seven drops) of stool suspension and respective test solutions were added to each tube. Normal saline served as the negative control, and liquid mebendazole as the positive control.

The seven (7) tubes were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours, 48 hours, 72 hours, and 7 days to simulate conditions inside the human body. The study conducted by Legesse *et al.* (2002) evaluated the efficacy of 100 mg mebendazole administered twice a day for three consecutive days for the treatment of *A. lumbricoides* and *T. trichiura* infections. Therefore, the researchers incubate the anthelmintic activity of the extracts and set a waiting period of up to 7 days to allow enough time for the extracts to take effect and enable us to assess the impact of potential treatments on worm eggs in a controlled setting, thereby facilitating the evaluation of their efficacy and the identification of their mechanisms of action (Hernando & Bouzat, 2024).

Evaluation of the Period of Incubation

The incubation period was used to evaluate the antiparasitic activity of *Allium fistulosum* crude and fresh extracts on helminth ova. Samples were incubated for 24, 48, and 72 hours, and up to 7 days, with daily observations of changes in the ova. After each incubation period, a wet mount was prepared by placing one drop of the incubated stool suspension and one drop of Lugol's iodine on a slide, then examined microscopically.

Evaluation of the Quantity of Ova

Simultaneously, the quality of helminth ova was also monitored closely. The number of ova was thoroughly counted by scanning the 10 fields of the prepared wet mount preparation. The counting and characterization of disintegrated ova were validated by a registered medical technologist. This was done to determine the effectiveness of the antiparasitic potential of *A. fistulosum* fresh and crude extract.

Evaluation of the Changes in the Appearance of Ova

The ovum was characterized in terms of its appearance after the specific period of incubation. The ova of *A. lumbricoides* and *T. trichiura* were evaluated based on the appearance of the embryo or larva inside the shell. If the plant crude extract is effective, the embryo or larva within was completely inactivated, with many tiny globules that were formed within the embryo or larva. According to Flota-Burgos *et al.* (2020), the morula, embryo, or larva of the ova of hookworms that are exposed to chemical substances and antiparasitic agents, such as extracts, shows signs of degeneration and a dehydrated appearance. Moreover, in a study conducted by Schmitz *et al.* (2016), their organism, *A. lumbricoides* ova, died and appeared non-viable by having a disfigured dark-oval structure and bubbled yolk or refractile granules inside the shell. Aside from the appearance inside the shell, another sign of the effectiveness of chemical substances is the disintegration or removal of the uterine layer of a mamillated *A. lumbricoides* ova (Brownell and Nelson, 2006).

Treatment of Data

The antiparasitic potential of the fresh and crude extract of *A. fistulosum* was assessed by characterizing the appearance of two tested organisms based on morphological changes in ova. The descriptive statistics present the calculated mean and standard deviation of the disintegration grade for each examined organism. The degree of degradation was recorded using a grading scale (0-3) for the various concentrations of the crude extract (25%, 50%, 75%, 100%), fresh extract, and the positive and negative controls.

Ethical Consideration

The study was approved by Saint Mary's University Research Ethics Board (SMUREB) with address and contact information at 2nd Floor, Rev. John Van Bauwel Hall, SMU Main Campus, Ponce

Street, Don Mariano Marcos, Bayombong, 3700 Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines (email: reb@smu.edu.ph; cellphone: 09177053041), with the code 2025 0861.

Laboratory safety

The procedure was scheduled and performed in the CNS laboratory with the supervision of a laboratory assistant. In handling and storing, the researchers ensured the stool specimen was collected in a dry, clean, leakproof container without any contamination from urine, water, soil, or other material contaminating the specimen (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), 2019). Prescribed Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) was worn through the process (this includes a lab gown, gloves, a mask, a hairnet, and goggles). Furthermore, the working area of the laboratory was decontaminated with alcohol before and after the laboratory experiment. At the end of the experiment, the gloves were removed and the hands were properly washed after completing any task involving the handling of fecal material, then sanitized the hands with alcohol along with the removal of PPE (hairnet, laboratory gown, and face mask) to avoid a high risk of infection (CDC, 2016). Other processes, such as autoclaving, were operated by a lab assistant.

Disposal of waste

The residuals from the plant sediments of *A. fistulosum* leaves materials after obtaining the extract were discarded into a biodegradable pit, and all biological waste, including samples containing helminth ova, must be properly decontaminated by pouring sodium hypochlorite (bleach) into the container before disposal. Contaminated equipment such as applicator sticks, slides, and used pipettes must also be properly disinfected with sodium hypochlorite (bleach) before disposing of them in their respective waste bins (CDC, 2016). Disposal should follow institutional and national guidelines to prevent environmental contamination. Any chemical solvents or reagents used in the extraction and testing process must be disposed of according to hazardous waste protocols. Neutralization or specialized disposal may be required based on the chemicals used.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Section 1. Percent Yield of *A. fistulosum* Crude Extract

To determine the efficiency of the plant extraction process, the yield of the crude extract was calculated in grams and subsequently converted into a percentage. To obtain the percent yield from *Allium fistulosum* crude extract, 350 grams of powdered plant material were extracted using ethanol as the solvent. In this experiment, 50g of solid residue (crude extract) after evaporation was obtained from the 350g of dry powder of *A. fistulosum*, resulting in a significant yield of 14.29%. As a result, a high yield obtained indicates that the extraction method is considered effective in producing a good amount of crude extract.

Therefore, the consistency of the obtained yield implied the efficiency of ethanol for extracting compounds from *A. fistulosum*. Specifically, the 14.29% yield points out an effective extraction process, strongly indicating that a substantial yield of active compounds was successfully isolated.

Section 2. Antiparasitic Activity of *Allium fistulosum* on Helminth Ova in Terms of Period of Incubation and Total Changes

Table 4 presents a comparative overview of the incubation periods of tubes containing the *A. fistulosum* extracts with *A. lumbricoides* and *T. trichiura*, two common soil-transmitted helminths affecting human populations. The table highlights the variations in incubation duration under an

optimal condition of 37°C for these two parasite ova, and it shows the illustration of the affected ova after subjecting them to their period of incubation.

Table 4
Period of incubation

Concentration	<i>A. lumbricoides</i>			
	24 hrs	48 hrs	72hrs	7 days
Negative Control				
Positive Control				
Fresh Extract				
100% Crude extract				
75% Crude extract				
50% Crude extract				
25% Crude extract				

Concentration	<i>T. trichiura</i>			
	24 hrs	48 hrs	72hrs	7 days
Negative Control				
Positive Control				
Fresh Extract				
100% Crude extract				
75% Crude extract				
50% Crude extract				
25% Crude extract				

The table above displays the morphological differences in *A. lumbricoides* and *T. trichiura* ova across varying concentrations of *A. fitulosum* extract and incubation periods, which suggest a concentration- and time-dependent ovicidal effect. At lower concentrations and shorter incubation times, the ova retain much of their structural integrity, with only minimal deformation. However, as the extract concentration increases and the exposure duration extends, the ova exhibit progressive structural damage, such as shell disintegration and distortion of the internal material. The result shows that the 7-day incubation period for *A. lumbricoides* ova is more effective compared to shorter durations of 24, 48, and 72 hours. The extended period of incubation is due to the duration effect of the positive control, which is the mebendazole. On the other hand, the results

revealed no significant effect against *T. trichiura* among all tested incubation periods. Despite the varying durations, the extracts had no significant effects on the ova of *T. trichiura*.

The observed antiparasitic activity of the extract suggests that its mechanism of action may target the structural and inner components of *A. lumbricoides* ova in 7 days. This effect highlights the susceptibility of soil-transmitted helminths after a sufficient amount of time. Clinically, the finding implies that the extract shows promising anthelmintic activity for *A. lumbricoides*, but it may not be suitable as a broad-spectrum treatment for other parasitic infections involving *T. trichiura*.

Table 5

Quantity and Characterization of the Changes in the Appearance of Ova

Concentration	Period of incubation	<i>A. lumbricoides</i>		<i>T. trichiuria</i>	
		Quantity	Quality (Characterization)	Quantity	Quality (Characterization)
Negative Control	24 hrs	0	0	0	0
	48 hrs	0	0	0	0
	72 hrs	0	0	0	0
	7 days	0	0	0	0
Positive Control	24 hrs	0	1.22	0	0
	48 hrs	0.67	2	0	0
	72 hrs	1.33	2.56	0	0
	7 days	12.33	2.67	0	0
Fresh Extract	24 hrs	0	1	0	0
	48 hrs	0.67	3	0	0
	72 hrs	1	2.44	0	0
	7 days	3.67	2.56	0	0
100% Crude extract	24 hrs	0	1.44	0	0
	48 hrs	1	2.22	0	0
	72 hrs	0.67	2.89	0	0
	7 days	5.67	2.22	0	0
75% Crude extract	24 hrs	0	1.56	0	0
	48 hrs	1	2.33	0	0
	72 hrs	1	2.56	0	0
	7 days	6.33	2.33	0	0
50% Crude extract	24 hrs	0	1.33	0	0
	48 hrs	0	1.89	0	0
	72 hrs	1	2.33	0	0
	7 days	4.33	2.78	0	0
25% Crude extract	24 hrs	0	1	0	0
	48 hrs	0	1.89	0	0
	72 hrs	0	2.11	0	0
	7 days	1.67	2.11	0	0

Evaluation of the Quantity of Ova

The table above shows the mean average of the three trials of the quantity of the disintegrated ova among the five (5) tested extracts and two (2) controls. This result was obtained by counting ten (10) ova (either normal or affected ova) in ten (10) fields; during counting, the number of affected ova showing degeneration was recorded from those ten (10) counted ova. The number of ova affected by the extract did not consistently increase with increasing concentration, which means that even though the extract has an antiparasitic effect on the ova, they often do not achieve complete eradication. The results revealed that the fresh extract has the highest quantity of disintegrated *A. lumbricoides* ova in the 7-day incubation period. Overall, the 75% and 100%

crude extracts and fresh extract have the highest quantity of disintegrated *A. lumbricoides* ova throughout the whole incubation period. The other crude extracts, 25% and 50%, along with the negative control, had fewer to no inactive ova among the tested incubation periods, suggesting a weaker or no impact on the integrity of the eggs. However, the results show that none of the extracts or controls worked against *T. trichiura* during any of the tested incubation periods, meaning no inactive or disintegrated ova were seen.

This result highlights the potential potency of the 75% and 100% crude extracts and fresh extract on *A. lumbricoides* ova but not on *T. trichiura* ova. Therefore, even though *A. fistulosum* may offer a natural alternative for controlling nematode populations; their application may be more effective for permeable egg shells or when used in conjunction with other antiparasitic agents to enhance efficacy.

Evaluation of the Changes in the Appearance of Ova

The table 5 on page 20 presents the final grading of the ova that showcases the disintegration effects caused by the different extracts. The qualitative assessment was based on the standardized criteria scale from 0 (no effect) to 3 (complete degradation). The gradings of the affected ova were obtained by getting the mean average of the gradings of four medical technologists per trial. The result shows that 75% and 100% crude extracts and fresh extracts have the most observed changes in the appearance of the ova of *A. lumbricoides*. This suggests that higher concentrations of the extract were associated with significantly greater structural degeneration or alterations of the ova, supporting the hypothesis that *A. fistulosum* possesses antiparasitic properties. As expected, there are still no observable changes in the appearance of *T. trichiura* ova in all extracts and controls among the tested incubation periods.

This finding suggests a threshold effect, where concentrations at or above 25% already produce a maximal antiparasitic response. This implies that *A. fistulosum* extract may effectively compromise the morphology of helminths with relatively permeable egg shells. However, its limited effect on the resilient ova of *T. trichiura* highlights species-specific limitations and the need for combination therapies.

IV. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

The study evaluated the antiparasitic potential of *Allium fistulosum* leaf extract against helminth ova, yielding 14.29% crude extract. Results showed that longer incubation periods, particularly 7 days, enhanced the ovicidal activity against *Ascaris lumbricoides* ova, with 75% and 100% crude extracts and fresh extract demonstrating high efficacy comparable to mebendazole. The extracts likely contain potent compounds that damage the ova's structural integrity. However, no effect was observed on *Trichuris trichiura* ova, and quantitative assessment was limited by the lack of a precise basis for measuring disintegration. Overall, the findings suggest *A. fistulosum* extract may be a promising treatment for *A. lumbricoides* infections, especially in low-resource settings.

Recommendations

1. Integrate bioactive compounds from green onions into functional foods or supplements to combat parasitic infections, especially in developing countries with high prevalence.
2. Study the effect of *A. fistulosum* crude extract against adult *T. trichiura*, as it may offer an effective natural alternative for treating this common parasite.

3. Formulate antiparasitic products against *A. lumbricoides* ova using *A. fistulosum* and evaluate their effects on living organisms to develop innovative treatments that can interrupt parasite transmission.
4. Explore the antiparasitic effect of *A. fistulosum* crude extract against other parasites, to test its efficacy on a broader range of parasites.

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